

The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai'

also known as "Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai", "Greco-Roman Statuary in Constantinople"

By Ethan Schmidt, Simon Fraser University

Entry tags: Hellenistic Religions, Religious Group, Text, Greek Religions, Medieval Christianity, Orthodoxy, Byzantine text

The Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai is an eighth or ninth century patriographic text which records brief notes on the examples of monumental Greco-Roman statuary of Constantinople and the numinous powers imputed to them. The exact circumstances and date of its composition, the identity of its author (or authors), and its purpose and genre remain subjects of contention among scholars. It preserves an image of Constantinople at a particular time in its history; the landscape which emerges is a scarcely-inhabited ruin, overgrown and dotted with enigmatic images invested with power in an antique time, and often filled with curious ex votos; tablets with riddlesome inscriptions, skeletons, strange figurines. Nevertheless, it arguably offers the student of Byzantine religion an opportunity to study the beliefs and powers imputed to Greco-Roman Statues in the medieval period. Moreover, as a text likely composed during the period of Iconoclasm (or just before it) it is notable that it concerns images, and, indeed, argues for their potency and importance (it is notable that even in the case of statues which work maleficent magic, the text cautions against destroying or molesting them). Furthermore, the wholesale reproduction of the Parastaseis in the widely-circulated tenth-century Patria, attests to continued engagement with the text as the centuries wore on.

Date Range: 700 CE - 900 CE

Region: Constantinople, c800CE-1400CE

Region tags: Byzantium

Constantinople, c800CE-1400CE

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Cameron, Averil, and Judith Herrin. *Constantinople in the Early Eighth Century: The Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai*. Leiden: Brill, 1984.
- Source 2: Chatterjee, Paroma. *Between the Pagan Past and the Christian Present in Byzantine Visual Culture: Statues in Constantinople, 4th-13th Centuries C.E.* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2022.
- Source 3: James, Liz. "Pray Not to Fall into Temptation and Be on Your Guard': Pagan Statues in Christian Constantinople." *Gesta* 35, no. 1 (1996): 12-20.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: N/A

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: N/A

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: The manuscript is housed at the BnF in Paris under the sobriquet Parisinus Graecus 1336.

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - No
- ↳ Domestic contexts
 - No
- ↳ Library/archive
 - Yes
- ↳ Specify
 - Specify: BnF

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1100 CE

Inked

–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Notes: Survives in a single codex unicus; Parisinus Graecus 1336.

Reference: Cameron, Averil , and Judith Herrin. Constantinople in the Early Eighth Century: The Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai. Leiden: Brill, 1984.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1100 CE

Specify type of paper

–Specify: Animal Membrane

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1100 CE

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1100 CE

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1100 CE

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1100 CE

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Notes: Survives in a single codex unicus; Parisinus Graecus 1336.

Reference: Cameron, Averil , and Judith Herrin. Constantinople in the Early Eighth Century: The Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai. Leiden: Brill, 1984.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1100 CE

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Animal Membrane

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1100 CE

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1100 CE

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Location

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[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

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↳ Mass Gathering Point
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↳ Cave(s)
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↳ Boundary markers or lines
– No

↳ Domestic contexts
– No

↳ Library/archive
– Yes

↳ Specify
– Specify: BnF

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text
This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.
– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?
– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?
– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?
– No

Are there clear reformist movements?
(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)
– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?
– No

Is there material significance to the text?
– Yes

↳ Is it visible?
– No

↳ Is it hidden?
– No

↳ Can it be touched?
– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?
– No

- ↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?
– No
- ↳ Does the text serve a protective function?
– No
- ↳ Does the text serve a healing function?
– No
- ↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?
– No
- ↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?
– No
- ↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?
– No
- ↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?
– No
- ↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?
– No
- ↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?
– I don't know
- ↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?
Please specify the substances in the sub-questions
– No

Production

- Is the production of the text funded by the polity?
– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

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– No
- ↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?
– I don't know
- ↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?
Please specify the substances in the sub-questions
– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: Beyond cautioning that Greco-Roman statues not be destroyed or damaged, the text is silent on social norms.

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: The text is predicated on Greco-Roman Statuary offering information regarding the future of the city and the empire, including at the end of the world. Though not specifically eschatological, these ideas of prophetic temporality are deeply engrained in the text.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

↳ Establishment of new political system

– Yes

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: The prophecies of the sculptures concern the fate of the city of Constantinople.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– No

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– No

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Death

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text itself seems to be a dossier of notes spanning many decades, if not more than a century, and compiled (most likely) in the 9th century.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– No

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The text belongs to a genre of 'Patriographic' literature, which describes the monuments of an ancient city, in this case Constantinople.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: Human remains are found sealed within statuary, but these do not necessarily represent formal burials as such.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– No

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Specify: The sculptures are endowed with prophetic powers and meanings, and, indeed, are quasi-animate. For example, a certain statue tumbles from its pedestal and crushes to death a certain 'Himerios', and it is later indicated by a certain philosopher that the sculpture, a portrait of the architect of the Kynegion, was prophesied to one day kill a man of rank.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can punish
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life
– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
– No

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life
– Yes

↳ In dreams
– No

↳ In trance possession
– No

↳ Through divination practices
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that it is necessary for those who are skilled in philosophy and prophetic interpretation of statuary to interpret the meaning of the messages expressed by the statues.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Communicate through other means

– Specify: N/A

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: Except obliquely in the sense that they exist in the Greco-Roman context in which these sculptures were created.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– No

↳ Food taboos?

– No

↳ Hair?

– No

↳ Dress?

– No

↳ Ornaments?

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: According to the Parastaseis, being able to interpret the meanings of the sculptures confers a special status and is connected to membership in the old senatorial elite of the capital.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text itself seems to be a dossier of notes spanning many decades, if not more than a century, and compiled (most likely) in the 9th century.

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– Other [specify]: The text belongs to a genre of 'Patriographic' literature, which describes the monuments of an ancient city, in this case Constantinople.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: N/A

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– I don't know

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

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Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

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↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

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↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

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↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

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↳ Have other knowledge of this world

–Specify: The sculptures are endowed with prophetic powers and meanings, and, indeed, are quasi-animate. For example, a certain statue tumbles from its pedestal and crushes to death a certain 'Himerios', and it is later indicated by a certain philosopher that the sculpture, a portrait of the architect of the Kynegion, was prophesied to one day kill a man of rank.

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- ↳ Human spirits can reward
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 - No
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - No
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 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - Yes
- Notes: In the sense that it is necessary for those who are skilled in philosophy and prophetic interpretation of statutory to interpret the meaning of the messages

expressed by the statues.

↳ Only through monarch
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↳ Communicate through other means
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Non-human supernatural beings are present

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Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

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Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

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Notes: Except obliquely in the sense that they exist in the Greco-Roman context in which these sculptures were created.

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Are other categories of beings present?

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Does the text guide divination practices?

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Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

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Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

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↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– No

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– No

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: Death

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: The text is predicated on Greco-Roman Statuary offering information regarding the future of the city and the empire, including at the end of the world. Though not specifically eschatological, these ideas of prophetic temporality are deeply engrained in the text.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

- ↳ At some other time [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: The prophecies of the sculptures concern the fate of the city of Constantinople.
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: Beyond cautioning that Greco-Roman statues not be destroyed or damaged, the text is silent on social norms.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– No

↳ Food taboos?

– No

↳ Hair?

– No

↳ Dress?

– No

↳ Ornaments?

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language?

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↳ Other?

– Specify: According to the Parastaseis, being able to interpret the meanings of the sculptures confers a special status and is connected to membership in the old senatorial elite of the capital.

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Presumably this text was produced by and for the literati, despite its solecistic and somewhat eccentric Greek.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No one was involved in the destruction of the text as far as is known

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– I don't know

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: If the interpreters of the statutory are to be considered teachers, they are meant to be consulted with reverence.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

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Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No one was involved in the destruction of the text as far as is known

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– I don't know

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: If the interpreters of the statutory are to be considered teachers, they are meant to be consulted with reverence.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', BERGER, ALBRECHT. "DAS CHALKUN TETRAPHYLON UND PARASTASEIS, KAPITEL 57". *Byzantinische Zeitschrift* 90, no. 1 (1997): 7-12. <https://doi.org/10.1515/byzs.1997.90.1.7>.
- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', Odorico, Paolo. "Du Recueil À L'invention Du Texte: Le Cas Des Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai". *Byzantinische Zeitschrift* 107, no. 2 (January 1, 2014): 755-84. <https://doi.org/10.1515/bz-2014-0019>.
- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', Millet, Gabriel. "Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai. Essai Sur La Date (en Grec)" 70, no. 1 (1946). <https://doi.org/10.3406/bch.1946.2589>.
- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', Anderson, Benjamin. "Classified Knowledge: The Epistemology of Statuary in The*<i>parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai</i>*". *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* 35, no. 1 (March 2011): 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1179/030701311x12906801091476>.
- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', Chatterjee, Paroma. "Viewing the Unknown in Eighth-century Constantinople". *Gesta* 56, no. 2 (September 2017): 137-49. <https://doi.org/10.1086/692801>.
- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', Chatterjee, Paroma. *Ancient Statues*, Christian City. Oxford University Press, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780190278359.003.0013>.
- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', Chatterjee, Paroma. *Between the Pagan Past and the Christian Present in Byzantine Visual Culture: Statues in Constantinople, 4th-13th Centuries C.E.*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2022.
- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', Mango, Cyril. "Antique Statuary and the Byzantine Beholder". *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 17, no. 1 (1963): 55-59.
- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', James, Liz. ""pray Not to Fall into Temptation and Be on Your Guard": Pagan Statues in Christian Constantinople". *Gesta* 35, no. 1 (1996): 12-20.
- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', Dagron, Gilbert. *Constantinople Imaginaire: Études Sur Le Recueil Des Patria*. Paris: Presses Universitaires de France, 1984.
- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', Saradi-Mendelovici, Helen. "Christian Attitudes Towards Pagan Monuments in Late Antiquity and Their Legacy in Later Byzantine Centuries". *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 44, no. 1 (1990): 47-61.
- Reference: The 'Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai', Cameron, Averil , and Judith Herrin. *Constantinople in the Early Eighth Century: The Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai*. Leiden: Brill, 1984.

Entry/Answer References

- Reference: Paper, Cameron, Averil , and Judith Herrin. *Constantinople in the Early Eighth Century: The Parastaseis Syntomoi Chronikai*. Leiden: Brill, 1984.